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Main Author(s)	Martyna Kusak (AMU), Karolina Kiejnich-Kruk (AMU), Kinga Krężel (AMU)
Document Reviewers	Denitsa Kozhuharova (LIF), Maria Lachova (LIF)

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Abbreviations

ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
ECtHR	European Court of Human Rights
ESO	European Supervision Order
EU	European Union
FD	Council Framework Decision

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Executive Summary

This Handbook builds upon data collected throughout the Release project, particularly practitioner-participants' experiences voiced in the events organised as part of the project. The different backgrounds represented by the target groups (judges, prosecutors and lawyers) helped to enable the collection and compilation of a cross-professional panorama of good practices and gaps. The Handbook is therefore based on different points of view, which will help to give a better understanding of how alternative measures can be applied at the national level and will facilitate mutual understanding and cooperation among different professionals – with the common goal of imposing pre-trial detention as a measure of last resort.

The Release project revealed difficulties in the application of the ECtHR standards relating to alternative measures. Therefore, the first section summarises the key points stemming from the relevant court case law. In addition, the Commission Recommendation (EU) 2023/681 is outlined to help with the navigation of the EU standards.

Section two includes best practices identified through the cross-professional activities. The key points for each profession are the following:

1) Lawyers:

- first actions with the suspect are often crucial in determining preventive measures. Lawyers help in gathering information, which may lead to the application of alternative measures to pre-trial detention;
- lawyers may help in a decision on alternative measures by explaining the particular situation of the suspect; and
- questioning the reasoning behind a decision to apply preventive measures can help to encourage ECtHR standards to be followed, and develops the practice of properly reasoned and justified decisions being made when these measures are imposed.

2) Prosecutors:

- individual evaluation of the suspect, reflected in a duly reasoned and justified decision on preventive measures, is needed in every case;
- collaboration with probation officers and the use of rehabilitation programmes may prove effective in specific circumstances (for example, if the suspect suffers from an addiction or mental issues); and
- in EU cross-border cases, a European Supervision Order may be used as an alternative to enable the cross-border supervision of non-custodial preventive measures.

3) Judges:

- an individual evaluation of the suspect's position when applying preventive measures is crucial;
- fair and detailed reasoning in the judicial decision, embedded in the individual circumstances of the case, is needed in every case; and
- judges should always consider applying a combination of measures, or a shorter period of pre-trial detention. Incorporation of ECtHR case law into national case law is recommended in this regard.

The last section gives an outline of European Supervision Order FD. This EU cooperation instrument enables the supervision of non-custodial preventive measures by the Member State in which the suspect resides whilst awaiting trial.

1. Introduction

The Handbook includes good practices identified by the Release project.

The project focused on alternatives to pre-trial detention in Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Slovakia and Poland. The overall goal of the project was to enhance the cooperation between practitioners working on cases involving pre-trial detention and alternatives to pre-trial detention. To this end, the project started by conducting data collection activities, including case law in the partner countries and ECtHR case law. The next step was the exchange of good practices and mutual

learning activities. This was carried out in domestic events, which took place in each partner country, as well as in two international events organised in Bratislava and Poznan.

The Release project is in line with the EU's efforts on alternatives to detention, which have been on the EU's agenda since 2004 when the Hague Programme recognised that detention and alternatives to detention were an important area of EU justice policy. In the 2019 Council Conclusions on Alternatives to Detention, Member States agreed that detention should be used only as a last resort and that, when appropriate, non-custodial sanctions and measures should be applied instead of detention, particularly with a view to the social rehabilitation and reintegration of offenders.¹ The same document confirmed that in many Member States pre-trial detention is not used as a measure of last resort and that alternatives to pre-trial detention are used to a very limited extent. Moreover, decisions on pre-trial detention are often not sufficiently reasoned and are not open to regular review, leading to long periods of pre-trial detention. These practices are reflected in the ECtHR case law on Articles 5(3) and 5(4) ECHR, relating to the EU Member States. The differences between the national systems and the use of detention measures and alternatives also raise problems for EU cooperation in criminal matters, particularly in the context of ESOs² (see Section 3).

This Handbook builds upon the data collected throughout the Release project, and particularly the practitioner-participants' experiences voiced in the events organised during the project. The different backgrounds of the target groups (judges, prosecutors and lawyers) enabled a cross-professional panorama of good practices and gaps to be collected and compiled. This Handbook is therefore based on different points of view, which will help to give a better understanding of how alternative measures can be applied at the national level and will facilitate mutual understanding and cooperation among different profes-

¹ <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-14075-2019-INIT/en/pdf>, p. 6.

² Ibidem, p. 3.

nals – with the common goal of imposing pre-trial detention as a measure of last resort.

1.1.The ECtHR standards on alternatives to pre-trial detention

The following section provides an overview of the key points stemming from the case law of the European Court of Human Rights relating to alternatives to pre-trial detention.

Obligation to consider alternatives to pre-trial detention	
Idalov v. Russia, § 140	When deciding whether a person should be released or detained, the authorities have an obligation under Article 5(3) ECHR to consider alternative measures for ensuring his or her appearance at trial.
Sulaoja v. Estonia, § 64	
Vrencev v. Serbia, § 76	Whenever the danger of absconding can be avoided by bail or other guarantees, the accused must be released, it being incumbent on the national authorities to always duly consider such alternatives.
Jabłoński v Poland, § 84	Consideration has to be given to the possibility of imposing other 'preventive measures' – such as bail or police supervision – to secure the proper conduct of the criminal proceedings.
Bail	
Muşuc v. Moldova, § 42	Bail may only be required for as long as reasons justifying detention prevail.
Toshev v. Bulgaria, § 68	<p>The amount set for bail must take into account the accused's:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - assets, - relationship with the persons who are to provide security, - citizenship, - age, and - occupation <p>so the prospect of loss of security, in the event of non-appearance at trial, will act as a sufficient deterrent to dispel any wish on his part to abscond.</p>

Iwańczuk v Poland, § 66	<p>Since the fundamental right to liberty guaranteed by Article 5 ECHR is at stake, the authorities must take as much care in fixing appropriate bail as they do in deciding whether or not the accused's continued detention is indispensable.</p>
Georgieva v. Bulgaria, §§ 15 and 30-31, Mangouras v. Spain, § 37	<p>The amount set for bail must be duly justified in the decision fixing bail.</p>
House arrest	
Buzadji v. The Republic of Moldova, § 104	<p>House arrest is considered, because of its degree and intensity, to amount to deprivation of liberty within the meaning of Article 5 ECHR.</p> <p>This type of deprivation of liberty requires relevant and sufficient reasons, just as with pre-trial detention.</p>
Navalny v. Russia, § 60	<p>The house arrest was ordered primarily on the grounds that the applicant had breached the previous preventive measure, an undertaking not to leave Moscow during the investigation, presumably indicating the risk of absconding.</p> <p>When imposing the house arrest, the domestic court had not indicated any specific facts which had not been previously identified, and had failed to show the emergence of those risks that would justify the application of house arrest.</p>
Restrictions on movement (Article 2 of Protocol to ECHR No. 4)	
Gochev v. Bulgaria, § 44	<p>Any measure restricting the right of movement must be in accordance with the law, pursue one of the legitimate aims referred to in the ECHR, and be necessary in a democratic society for the achievement of that aim.</p> <p>Such a measure must strike a fair balance between the public interest and the individual's rights.</p>

**Popoviciu v.
Romania, §§
91,95**

The restriction on movement may be justified in a given case only if there are clear indications of a genuine public interest which outweighs the individual's right to freedom of movement.

Periodic reassessment on maintaining restrictions on an individual's freedom of movement for a lengthy period is mandatory.

**Miażdżyk v.
Poland, § 35**

The duration of the restriction in itself cannot be taken as the sole basis for determining whether a fair balance was struck between the general interest in the proper conduct of the criminal proceedings and the applicant's personal interest in enjoying freedom of movement.

**Popoviciu v.
Romania, §
91**

This issue must be assessed according to all the special features of the case.

The restriction may be justified in a given case only if there are clear indications of a genuine public interest which outweighs the individual's right to freedom of movement.

**Popoviciu v.
Romania**

Example of the Court finding no violation of freedom of movement. The specifics of the case are the following:

- the prohibition on leaving the country was imposed for a period of three months and eight days;
- the applicant had the opportunity to challenge the application of the preventive measure before the courts, and pleaded that the measure had prevented him from pursuing his business, which involved travel abroad;
- there was a reasonable suspicion that the applicant had committed the offence with which he had been charged, and that revoking the restriction would impede the proper administration of justice;
- the complex nature of the proceedings against the applicant, which involved extensive evidence, could justify, for a limited period of time, the prohibition on the applicant's leaving the country so that his immediate presence could be ensured if necessary;
- a reassessment took place every thirty days; and
- the domestic courts lifted the preventive measure imposed on the applicant when they considered that it was no longer necessary for the proper administration of justice, although the criminal proceedings against him were still pending.

**Antonenkov
and Others v.
Ukraine**

Example of the Court finding no violation of freedom of movement. The specifics of the case are the following:

- the obligation not to leave their area of residence was imposed on the applicants for a period of approximately five years and three months;
- the preventive measures were not automatically applied for the whole duration of the criminal proceedings; and
- whenever the applicants applied to leave their place of residence they were granted permission.

A.E. v Poland

Example of the Court finding there was a violation of freedom of movement. In this case, a travel ban was imposed for a period of eight years, and:

- a reassessment took place only once, at the applicant's request, which would indicate that the travel ban was in reality an automatic, blanket measure of indefinite duration; and
- the Court considered that this ran counter to the authorities' duty under Article 2 of Protocol No. 4 to take appropriate care to ensure that any interference with the applicant's right to leave Poland remained justified and proportionate throughout its duration.

**Prescher v
Bulgaria**

Example of the Court finding there was a violation of freedom of movement. In this case, the ban on leaving the country lasted for about five years and three months. The Court reiterated that:

- even if justified at the outset, a measure restricting an individual's freedom of movement may become disproportionate if it is extended over a long period; and
- the authorities did not consider whether the applicant's presence continued to be necessary after so many years of investigation.

Police supervision

**Zmarzlak v.
Poland, §§
44-52**

The applicant was under police supervision for a period of 12 years. The ECtHR stated that:

- the risk that a person charged may disrupt the proper course of proceedings decreases over time;
- any measure that results in limiting the freedom to exercise rights relating to the sphere of an individual's private life must be interpreted narrowly and applied with restraint; and
- it is for the authorities to ensure that measures restricting the rights and freedoms of an individual do not jeopardise the maintenance of a fair balance between the interests of that individual and the general interest, in this case respect for the interests of justice.

The Court found a violation of Article 8 ECHR (right to privacy).

Forfeiture of bail

**Lavrechov v.
The Czech
Republic, §§
43-57**

Although a forfeiture of bail constitutes interference by the state with the applicant's property rights, it pursues the legitimate aim of ensuring the proper conduct of criminal proceedings and, more generally, of fighting and preventing crime, which undoubtedly falls within the general interest as envisaged in Article 1 of Protocol No. 1.

Turning to the proportionality test, the Court noted that the bail of approximately EUR 400,000 was a substantial amount of money, but stated that the appropriate time for discussing the proportionality of the amount of security for bail is when the bail is set, not when it is forfeited.

1.2. Commission Recommendation (EU) 2023/681 of 8 December 2022 on procedural rights of suspects and accused persons subject to pre-trial detention and on material detention conditions

The Recommendation³ sets out guidance for the way in which Member States should take effective, appropriate and proportionate measures to strengthen the rights of all suspects and accused persons in criminal proceedings who are deprived of their liberty, including strengthening the rule that deprivation of liberty can only be used as a measure of last resort.⁴ Extracts from the Recommendations are presented below.

Commission Recommendation 2023/681	
Definitions (5)	'Alternative measures' should be understood as less restrictive measures as an alternative to detention.
General principles (10)	Member States should use pre-trial detention only as a measure of last resort. Alternative measures to detention should be preferred, in particular where the offence is punishable only by a short sentence of imprisonment or where the offender is a child.
Minimum standards for procedural rights of suspects and accused persons subject to pre-trial detention (14)	Member States should impose pre-trial detention only where strictly necessary and as a measure of last resort, taking due account of the specific circumstances of each individual case. To this end, Member States should apply alternative measures where possible.

³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32023H0681>.

⁴ General Principles (10).

Minimum standards for procedural rights of suspects and accused persons subject to pre-trial detention (15)

Member States should adopt a presumption in favour of release. Member States should require the competent national authorities to bear the burden of proof for demonstrating the necessity of imposing pre-trial detention.

Minimum standards for procedural rights of suspects and accused persons subject to pre-trial detention (16)

To avoid inappropriate use of pre-trial detention, Member States should make available the widest possible range of alternative measures, such as the alternative measures mentioned in Council Framework Decision 2009/829/JHA on the application of the principle of mutual recognition to decisions on supervision measures as an alternative to provisional detention.

Minimum standards for procedural rights of suspects and accused persons subject to pre-trial detention (22)

Member States should ensure that every decision by a judicial authority to impose pre-trial detention, to prolong such pre-trial detention, or to impose alternative measures is duly reasoned and justified and refers to the specific circumstances of the suspect or accused person justifying their detention. The person affected should be provided with a copy of the decision, which should also include reasons why alternatives to pre-trial detention are not considered appropriate.

2. Good practices

2.1. Lawyers

Key points

- First actions with the suspect are often crucial in determining preventive measures. **Lawyers** help in gathering information, which may lead to the application of alternative measures to pre-trial detention.
- Lawyers may help in a decision on alternative measures by explaining the particular situation of the suspect.
- Questioning the reasoning behind a decision on preventive measures can help to encourage ECtHR standards to be followed, and develops the practice of properly reasoned and justified decisions being made when these measures are imposed.

2.2.

2.2.1. Early assistance for the suspect

The first actions of the defence lawyer depend on the situation of the suspect against whom preventive measures are to be applied – that is, on whether or not the suspect has been detained.

If the suspect has been detained, it is crucial for the lawyer to act promptly. The sooner he/she is informed about the detention, the sooner he/she can take the necessary actions. As a first step, it is good practice to make an effort to talk to the suspect as soon as possible.⁵

If the suspect is already a client of the lawyer, it is most likely that his/her family members will notify the lawyer of the arrest. In such cases the lawyer is

⁵ Some lawyers have an on-call system at their law offices, so that someone will always be available to start acting at any time. Other lawyers simply provide a number on which they are always available.

often familiar with the situation of the detained, and it is easier to take action on alternative measures. If the first contact with the suspect is only after the arrest, it is also important to talk to the suspect's relatives, since they will be the ones who will be able to indicate, even before the lawyer talks to the suspect, whether the suspect has any health problems, how he behaved during the arrest, or what property surety can be offered during the proceedings.

In a situation of police detention, pre-trial detention is most often considered. If the suspect is summoned to appear voluntarily because of their activities, there is a good chance that pre-trial detention will not be considered at all.

During the interrogation of the suspect (either on their detention or during a voluntary appearance), the participation of the lawyer is extremely important. At the beginning of the interrogation, personal data are collected: the age of the suspect, his/her residential address and contact information, and details on his/her family, health and financial situation. This information is important for the application of preventive measures, as it can determine whether non-custodial measures are also a realistic option.

The participation of the lawyer in the interrogation will also enable the lawyer to control what the suspect explains and whether his/her rights are respected. The suspect's behaviour can affect which preventive measures will be applied, which is why it is so important to have the lawyer present with the suspect.

It should be pointed out that the issue of whether the suspect is a client of a lawyer of choice or a lawyer appointed ex officio does not affect the quality of the legal assistance, but it does affect the point in time at which the lawyer has information about the suspect's arrest and can proceed to give assistance.

In the case of Šebalj v. Croatia (application no. 4429/09) the ECtHR noted that the participation of a lawyer in the first actions taken in respect of a suspect is crucial in the case. If the lawyer did not participate in these actions, even if he participated at a later stage, a situation may arise in which any defects that occurred during the actions conducted without his participation can no longer be remedied.

In the case of Płonka v. Poland (application no. 20310/02) the ECtHR emphasised that a suspect should have a real possibility of being assisted by a lawyer at the early stages of pre-trial proceedings, and preferably from the very first hearing in the case.

2.2.2. Proactive role in proposing alternatives to pre-trial detention

The defence lawyer, as the person who protects the suspect's interests, can take the initiative to propose non-custodial preventive measures instead of pre-trial detention.

Before submitting a proposal for non-custodial measures, the lawyer should take into account the suspect's personal situation and the details of the case in which these measures are to be applied. This increases the chances that the proposal will be taken into account.

Where appropriate, it is worth suggesting a combination of alternative measures. According to the Release project target group, the most effective alternatives to pre-trial detention are:

- 1) In Bulgaria – house arrest (especially combined with electronic monitoring) and bail.
- 2) In Croatia – house arrest with electronic monitoring and bail.

- 3) In Greece – house arrest with electronic monitoring.
- 4) In Poland – bail and police supervision combined with a ban on leaving the country.
- 5) In Slovakia – bail and supervision of the accused by a probation or mediation officer.

2.2.3. Preparing for the court session at which the request for pre-trial detention is to be considered

If the court is to consider a request for pre-trial detention, the lawyer must prepare properly for, and attend, this court session. It is extremely important to get acquainted with the case file. Such cases (especially if police detention is at stake) present a significant challenge for all parties involved (prosecutors, judges and lawyers), who all work around the clock, and there are often practical difficulties with obtaining access to case files.

While awaiting access to the file, the lawyer can learn about the suspect's situation in another way, by talking to his relatives. It is the relatives who will be able to explain the defendant's health, family and financial situation. They are also the ones who will help determine what alternative measures can be proposed in the situation.

In the case of Dochnal v. Poland (application no. 31622/07), the ECtHR indicated that it is essential for the lawyer to have access to the file and to inspect the documents in it, subject, if need be, to special arrangements in respect of classified documents, in order to challenge the lawfulness of the applicant's pre-trial detention.

Judges often expect the lawyer, who knows about the suspect's individual position, to be proactive and propose measures that may be considered as alternatives to pre-trial detention.

2.2.4. Questioning the reasoning for a decision on preventive measures

The Release project identified the need for proper justification of decisions relating to pre-trial detention and alternative measures. Therefore, it is considered to be good practice to challenge the justification given for a ruling on a preventive measure itself, in case it lacks links to the specific circumstances of the case.

Every decision to impose or prolong preventive measures (either pre-trial detention or alternative measures) should be duly reasoned and justified and refer to the specific circumstances of the suspect or accused person, as set out in the ECtHR and EU standards (see Sections 1.1 and 1.2).

2.2.5. Awareness-raising with predictive tools

Given the increasing use of AI-based predictive tools supporting, among other things, an evaluation of the risk of reoffending, lawyers should develop skills that will help them verify the use of such tools. Despite the general ban on using automated decision-making under EU data protection law, predictive policing may still be used to support decision-making. As a result, lawyers need to be prepared for these new tools to play a role in decisions related to the application of preventive measures.

2.2. Prosecutors

Key points

- Individual evaluation of the suspect, reflected in a duly reasoned and justified decision on preventive measures, is needed in every case.
- Collaboration with probation officers and the use of rehabilitation programmes may prove effective in specific circumstances (for example, if the suspect suffers from an addiction or mental issues).
- In EU cross-border cases, an ESO may be used as an alternative to enable the cross-border supervision of non-custodial preventive measures.

2.3.

2.3.1. An individual evaluation of the suspect's position

Every case involving preventive measures requires an individual evaluation of the suspect's position, even though some aspects of the case may be similar to aspects of other cases. Therefore, it is good practice to consider all the circumstances of the case and, in particular, the age of the suspect, his/her family situation, his/her links to the place where he/she is staying, his/her health situation (both mental and physical), the nature of the act, the time that has elapsed since the act was committed, the suspect's relationship with the victim and witnesses to the proceedings, the criminal history of the suspect and his/her attitude to the proceedings so far, the stage of the proceedings, and the scope of evidence collected so far.

2.3.2. A duly reasoned and justified decision

Despite the practical difficulties stemming from the time pressure that often comes with cases on preventive measures (especially those involving police detention), it is essential to provide specific case-related reasoning, as emphasised by the ECtHR (see Sections 1.1 and 1.2).

Therefore, it is of the utmost importance to ensure that every decision imposing alternative measures is reasoned and justified and refers to the specific circumstances of the case. This requirement also applies to:

- a prosecutor's application for pre-trial detention (or its prolongation), which should include reasons why alternatives to pre-trial detention are not considered appropriate; and
- every decision imposing preventive measures.

In the case of Mangouras v. Spain, the Court pointed out that, according to its case law, the amount of bail must be assessed principally 'by reference to [the person concerned], his assets ..., in other words to the degree of confidence that is possible that the prospect of loss of the security ... in case of his non-appearance at the trial will act as a sufficient deterrent to dispel any wish on his part to abscond'.

In the case of Navalny v. Russia, which related to a house arrest, the ECtHR stated that the domestic court did not indicate any specific facts which had not been previously identified, and thus had failed to show the emergence of those risks that would justify the application of house arrest.

2.3.3. Considering a combination of alternative measures

In all the partner Member States in the project, there is a possibility of applying a combination of those alternative measures which may best correspond with the circumstances of the case and the individual position of the suspect. According to the project's target group, the most effective alternatives to pre-trial detention are:

- 1) In Bulgaria – house arrest (especially combined with electronic monitoring) and bail.
- 2) In Croatia – house arrest with electronic monitoring and bail.
- 3) In Greece – house arrest with electronic monitoring.

- 4) In Poland – bail and police supervision combined with a ban on leaving the country.
- 5) In Slovakia – bail and supervision of the accused by a probation or mediation officer.

2.3.4. Collaboration with probation officers and use of rehabilitation programmes

The Release project revealed that it is good practice to combine alternative measures with rehabilitation programmes and, where possible, to engage probation officers who can also offer counselling to suspects. This has been proved to be effective for suspects with an addiction or mental issues, especially in cases relating to domestic violence where pre-trial detention is often used to prevent another offence being committed against the victim. Probation officers may operate in place of or alongside the police force (e.g. through supervision measures), and rehabilitation programmes may be either custodial or non-custodial.

2.3.5. Access to case files and disclosure of relevant evidence

It is crucial for all the actors involved (particularly the defence team) to have full information about the data and evidence on which the decision on preventive measures is based. This presents a significant challenge for all the parties involved (prosecutors, judges, and lawyers) when a suspect has been detained by the police and the court must quickly decide whether to prolong the detention or apply a non-custodial measure. In such cases, all the parties, including the prosecutors, will work around the clock, and access to case files often depends on practicalities. Therefore, it is advisable to allow the defence to have access to the case file as soon as possible, to give them sufficient time to prepare their arguments and present them in writing or orally at the hearing. It is recommended that, where feasible, digitised files be made available in lieu of

paper files. This enables all parties involved in the proceedings to consult the file simultaneously.

In the case of Cviková v. Slovakia (applications nos. 615/21, 9427/21 and 36765/21), the ECtHR emphasised that, to allow the possibility of a real challenge being made to the basis of the allegations and the use of preventive measures, the lawyer must be given access to documents in the case file which form the basis of the prosecution case against the suspect. Equality of arms is not ensured if counsel is denied access to those documents in the investigation file which are essential in order to put an effective challenge to the lawfulness of his client's detention.

It is also important that, when disclosing evidence on which the motion requesting pre-trial detention or the use of alternative measures is based, the prosecutor makes sure that this is both comprehensive and relevant to the case.

2.3.6. Conscious use of predictive policing tools

Predictive tools are designed to ascertain the likelihood of an event occurring. It is recommended that these tools should not be relied on to too great an extent, and that transparency should be exercised with regard to the use of such tools and their source code. This allows the parties involved in the proceedings to ascertain the basis on which the result was reached, namely the input data and rules applied, thus enabling them to present appropriate counterarguments on appeal.

2.3.Judges

Key points

- An individual evaluation of the suspect's position when applying preventive measures is crucial.
- Fair and detailed reasoning in the judicial decision, embedded in the individual circumstances of the case, is needed in every case.
- Judges should always consider applying a combination of measures, or a shorter period of pre-trial detention. Incorporation of ECtHR case law into national case law is recommended in this regard.

2.4.

2.4.1.An individual evaluation of the suspect's position

Every case involving preventive measures requires an individual evaluation of the suspect's position, even though some aspects of the case may be similar to aspects of other cases. Therefore, it is good practice to consider all the circumstances of the case and, in particular, the age of the suspect, his/her family situation, his/her links to the place where he/she is staying, his/her health situation (both mental and physical health), the nature of the act, the time that has elapsed since the act was committed, the suspect's relationship with the victim and witnesses to the proceedings, the criminal history of the suspect and his/her attitude to the proceedings so far, the stage of the proceedings, and the scope of the evidence collected so far. In particular, consideration should be given to whether there is a need for pre-trial detention in white-collar crime cases in which evidence has already been gathered (mainly from documents) and the charges do not involve an allegation that the suspect was part of an organised criminal group.

In the Croatian criminal case NR: U-III/3023/2021, the applicant was charged with human trafficking, and lodged a complaint with the Constitutional Court concerning the unjustified application of pre-trial detention. The rationale provided for the detention was the perceived risk of reoffending. The applicant, who was the mother of a six-month-old child who was being breastfed, argued that the Court had failed to consider the impact of the extension of the applicant's pre-trial detention. The Court agreed that the criminal court had failed to consider the rationale behind the restriction of liberty. As a mother of a six-month-old infant who is being breastfed, it would have been reasonable to expect that sufficient care would have been taken. According to the reasoning of the Constitutional Court, it would have been prudent to assess the circumstances of the case in order to ascertain the possibility of imposing pre-trial detention at the applicant's home.

2.4.2.A comprehensive examination of the case files and the request for pre-trial detention

Full knowledge of the case files and the reasons for the application for pre-trial detention ensure that every aspect of the case is given full consideration. This, however, presents a significant challenge in circumstances in which the suspect has been arrested and the court is afforded a limited timeframe (typically 24 hours) to determine whether pre-trial detention is appropriate. Therefore, it is recommended that the judge responsible for determining pre-trial detention cases for a specified period should limit their other professional obligations by, for instance, avoiding scheduling additional hearings and proceedings during their designated duty hours. The on-call schedule for pre-trial detention could be divided among judges well in advance to optimise decision-making time.

Furthermore, judges should recognise that time limitations in pre-trial detention cases also pose challenges for the defence and prosecutors. It is therefore

advisable to permit defence counsel to access the case file as soon as possible, to give them sufficient time to prepare their arguments and present them in writing or orally at the hearing. It is recommended that, where feasible, digitised files be made available in lieu of paper files. This enables all parties involved in the proceedings to consult the file simultaneously.

In Slovakia, the Supreme Court (Judgement No. 3 Tost 34/2020) placed significant emphasis on the necessity for the accurate judicial examination of the circumstances of the case. For example, in this case, the legal classification of the alleged crime as a 'particularly serious crime' – precluding the possibility of replacing custody with one of the alternatives to pre-trial detention – was deemed to be arbitrary and in violation of the complainant's right to personal liberty. In the view of the Slovakian Constitutional Court, it is unconstitutional for the misconduct of law enforcement agencies (by exaggerating the crime) to preclude the possibility of alternatives to pre-trial detention. For this reason, a comprehensive judicial examination of the case circumstances is always required.

2.4.3.A duly reasoned and justified decision

The parties involved should know all the reasons behind a decision on preventive measures. The decision should make direct reference to the specific circumstances of the case in question, together with references to the specific arguments presented by the parties (in accordance with the ECtHR and EU standards, see Sections 1.1 and 1.2).

In the context of pre-trial detention, it is, moreover, necessary to provide precise and well-founded reasons as to why the alternatives are not sufficient, with a focus on the specific circumstances of the case rather than on general principles. In instances in which a decision on pre-trial detention must be made with minimal delay, it can be challenging, if not impossible, to present a comprehensive written rationale that addresses each argument raised by the parties

during the hearing. Nevertheless, it is preferable that the decision to deprive an individual of their liberty should be sufficiently reasoned and contain a detailed rationale, at least with regard to the key arguments.

In the case of Porowski v. Poland, 34458/03, the applicant alleged that his detention on remand had been unlawful and had exceeded a reasonable time. In that regard, the ECtHR emphasised that a person charged with an offence must always be released pending trial unless the state can show that there are relevant and sufficient reasons to justify his continued detention. The domestic courts must examine all the arguments for and against the existence of a genuine requirement of public interest that justifies, with due regard to the principle of the presumption of innocence, a departure from the rule of respect for individual liberty, and must set these arguments out in their decision on an application for release. The ECtHR emphasised that, when deciding whether a person should be released or detained, the authorities have an obligation under Article 5(3) of the ECHR to consider alternative measures to ensure his or her appearance at trial. In the present case the ECtHR concluded that there had been a violation of Article 5(3).

In a Polish domestic criminal case, II AKz 327/20 (Court of Appeal in Szczecin), the District Court annulled a detention order and applied preventive measures in the form of bail for each of the accused individuals, who were charged with drug dealing. The Court of Appeal upheld this decision. In its written justification, it stated that the deprivation and limitation of personal liberty should be interpreted rigorously, given that the constitutional and conventional value that is subject to legal protection is the personal freedom of an individual, as set forth in the Constitution of the Republic of Poland and Article 5(1) of the ECHR. The use of pre-trial detention is permitted only in exceptional circumstances. Preventive measures, which are designed to protect individuals, cannot be used for the convenience of the authorities conducting the proceedings or for the purpose of determining a specific factual state. Rather, they can only be employed to secure the proper course of criminal proceedings. The principal conclusions to be drawn from this judicial decision are that pre-trial detention should be regarded as a measure of last resort and that each decision to extend detention should be considered on its own merits. At the time of making a decision, a court should conduct a fresh analysis of the circumstances, rather than repeating the arguments presented previously.

2.4.4. Considering a combination of measures or the application of a shorter period of pre-trial detention

It is prudent to evaluate, in a consistent way, the suitability of available measures for ensuring the appropriate course of proceedings, and to decide which of the available measures is most likely to achieve the desired result in the least invasive manner. Although pre-trial detention is an effective measure with a high success rate, some proceedings can be pursued without resorting to the deprivation of liberty. It is therefore advisable for judges to consider, on a case-by-case basis, whether alternative measures, or a combination of alternative measures, will suffice to achieve the desired result. If the aforementioned ana-

lysis yields unfavourable results, it is imperative to ascertain the shortest detention period that allows the objectives of the preventive measure to be achieved. It is not advisable to automatically apply the measure for the maximum permissible period, but instead to consider whether a short detention will suffice, with the recognition that it may be extended if necessary.

In Decision no. 359/2021 the 9th Athens Investigating Judge (Greece) ruled that replacing pre-trial detention with electronic monitoring fulfils the aim of preventing the risk that the accused will commit new crimes and ensures that the accused will be present at the trial and will be subjected to the sentence. After six months of pre-trial detention, the detention was terminated and substituted with a non-custodial measure. The restrictive measure which was imposed included restriction at home with electronic monitoring. The judge held that the applicant had a permanent address, and required him to pay all the expenses of installing and operating the electronic system. The judge concluded that 'the legitimate aim is pursued and is harmonised with the principle of proportionality between the means employed and the aim sought to be achieved'.

2.4.5. The incorporation of ECtHR case law into the domestic case law landscape

The extensive jurisprudence of the ECtHR provides a substantial number of examples of both effective and ineffective practices in the implementation of precautionary measures. A considerable number of states have been unsuccessful in proceedings concerning violations of Article 5 ECHR, particularly in the context of the abuse of pre-trial detention and the inadequate justification of decisions pertaining to its use. It is therefore of great importance that national jurisprudence draws upon the ECtHR's *acquis*. It is of equal relevance that national jurisprudence evolves in alignment with the direction indicated by the Court, namely by requiring a of detailed examination and explanation of the use of pre-trial detention and an increase in the use of alternative measures in cases

where detention is not deemed necessary. It is imperative that supreme courts, courts of appeal, and first instance courts engage in the transfer of good practice from ECtHR case law to national jurisprudence.

In a Slovakian criminal case concerning the issue of pre-trial detention (with reference number 39Tp/13/2020), the judge presiding over the preliminary hearing referred to the ECHR. He stated that it was possible to rely on Article 5(3) ECHR, which allows a person to be released on condition that they are available to the law enforcement authorities. Following the case law of the ECtHR, the potential danger posed by an individual accused of a serious crime and facing a potentially lengthy sentence of imprisonment could not be determined solely on the basis of the gravity of the crime and the anticipated punishment. It is incumbent upon state authorities to consider the possibility of securing the accused with alternative measures, such as bail or supervision. The judge presiding over the preliminary hearing reached the conclusion that, by replacing pre-trial detention with the supervision of a probation and mediation officer and the simultaneous imposition of appropriate restrictions and obligations, together with the obligation to submit to a check by technical means, it was possible to achieve the purpose of pre-trial detention in the given case.

2.4.6. Conscious use of predictive policing tools

In the light of the growing deployment of profiling and predictive policing technologies in the context of preventive measures, particularly in the assessment of the risk of recidivism, everyone, but especially judges, should bear in mind that such tools do not predict the future.

Predictive tools are designed to ascertain the likelihood of an event occurring. It is recommended that these tools should not be relied on to too great an extent, and that transparency should be exercised with regard to the use of such tools and their source code. This allows the parties involved in the proce-

edings to ascertain the basis on which the result was reached, namely the input data and rules applied, thus enabling them to present appropriate counterarguments on appeal.

3. European Supervision Order

European Supervision Order was introduced by the Framework Decision 2009/829⁶ and subsequently implemented by the Member States into their domestic laws.

The FD promotes, where appropriate, the use of non-custodial measures as an alternative to provisional detention in cases with a cross-border component. In such cases, there is a risk of different treatment between those who are resident in the trial state and those who are not: a non-resident may be remanded in custody pending trial even when, in similar circumstances, a resident would not. An ESO offers an alternative by promoting, where appropriate, the use, in the course of criminal proceedings, of non-custodial measures for persons who are not resident in the Member State in which the proceedings are taking place.⁷

ESOs are EU instruments based on mutual recognition for judicial cooperation in criminal matters. They enable a competent authority in one Member State (the issuing authority) to require supervision measures imposed on a non-resident suspect as an alternative to pre-trial detention to be supervised by the authorities in another Member State (the executing authority) in which the suspect is residing whilst awaiting trial.

European Supervision Orders

⁶ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec_framw/2009/829/oj.

⁷ Recitals 4 and 5 of the FD 2009/829.

Subject-matter	ESOs enable a judicial authority in one Member State (the issuing authority) to require supervision measures imposed on a non-resident suspect as an alternative to pre-trial detention to be supervised by the authorities in another Member State (the executing authority) in which she/he is a resident whilst awaiting trial.
Issuing	<p>An issuing authority may forward a decision on supervision measures on its own initiative or upon the suspect's request.</p> <p>Such a decision must be accompanied by a certificate (the standard form set out in Annex I to the Framework Decision 2009/829).</p>
Member State to which the decision on supervision measures may be forwarded	<p>An ESO can be forwarded to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the Member State in which the person is 'lawfully and ordinarily residing', if the person consents; or • at the defendant's request, a Member State other than that in which s/he ordinarily resides, but in such a case the consent of that Member State is required.
Recognition and execution	The executing authority shall, as soon as possible and in any case within 20 working days of receipt of the decision on supervision measures and the certificate, recognise the decision on supervision measures and without delay take all necessary measures to monitor the supervision measures, unless it decides to invoke one of the grounds for non-recognition referred to in Article 15 of the Framework Decision 2009/829.
Adaptation of the supervision measures	<p>Adaptation of the supervision measures imposed by the issuing authority is possible if the nature of the supervision measures is incompatible with the law of the executing state.</p> <p>In such cases, the competent executing authority may adapt the measures in line with the type of supervision measures which apply, under the law of the executing state, to equivalent offences. The adapted supervision measure must correspond as far as possible to that imposed in the issuing state and must not be more severe than the supervision measure which was originally imposed.</p> <p>Any decision to adapt the supervision measure must be communicated to the issuing authority, which may decide to withdraw the ESO if monitoring in the executing state has not yet begun.</p>
Breach of the supervision measures	If the suspect breaches the supervision measures, the procedures envisaged in the executing state shall apply. This could also lead to the issuing of a European arrest warrant.

4. Relevant legislation

4.1. EU legal instruments and other documents

Commission Recommendation (EU) 2023/681 of 8 December 2022 on procedural rights of suspects and accused persons subject to pre-trial detention and on material detention conditions, C/2022/8987, OJ L 86, 24 March 2023 available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32023H0681>

Council Framework Decision of 13 June 2002 on the European arrest warrant and the surrender procedure between Member States, 2002/584/JHA, OJ L 190, 18 July 2002 available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32002F0584>

Council Framework Decision on the application of the principle of mutual recognition to judgments and probation decisions with a view to the supervision of probation measures and alternative sanctions, 2008/947/JHA, OJ L 337, 16 December 2008, available at: https://eurlex.europa.eu/eli/dec_framw/2008/947/oj

Council Framework Decision on the application between Member States of the European Union, of the principle of mutual recognition to decisions on supervision measures as an alternative to provisional detention, 2009/829/JHA, OJ L 294, 11 November 2009, available at: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec_framw/2009/829/oj

Directive 2010/64/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 October 2010 on the right to interpretation and translation in criminal proceedings, OJ L 280, 26 October 2010

Directive 2012/13/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2012 on the right to information in criminal proceedings, OJ L 142, 1 June 2012

Directive 2013/48/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 October 2013 on the right of access to a lawyer in criminal proceedings and in European arrest warrant proceedings, and on the right to have a third party informed upon deprivation of liberty and to communicate with third persons and with consular authorities while deprived of liberty, OJ L 294, 6 November 2013

Directive (EU) 2016/800 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 May 2016 on procedural safeguards for children who are suspects or accused persons in criminal proceedings, OJ L 132, 21 May 2016

Directive (EU) 2016/1919 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 October 2016 on legal aid for suspects and accused persons in criminal proceedings and for requested persons in European arrest warrant proceedings, OJ L 297, 4 November 2016

Draft Council conclusions on alternative measures to detention, 14075/19, available at: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-14075-2019-INIT/en/pdf>

4.2. Council of Europe legal documents

Council of Europe, European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, as amended by Protocols Nos. 11 and 14, 4 November 1950, ETS 5

Council of Europe, Recommendation Rec(2006)2 of the Committee of Ministers to Member States on the European Prison Rules, Strasbourg, 11 January 2006

Council of Europe, Committee of Ministers, Recommendation Rec(2006)13 on the use of remand in custody, the conditions in which it takes place and the provision of safeguards against abuse, 27 September 2006

4.3. National legal frameworks

Bulgarian Criminal Procedure Code (Published State Gazette No. 86/28.10.2005, effective 29 April 2006, amended, SG No. 46/12.06.2007, effective 1 January 2008)

Croatian Criminal Procedure Code (Official Gazette, No. 152/08, 76/09, 80/11, 121/11, 91/12, 143/12, 56/13, 145/13, 152/14, 70/17, 126/19, 130/20, 80/22).

Greek Criminal Procedure Code

Polish Criminal Procedure Code (Act of 6 June 1997)

Slovak Criminal Procedure Code (Act 300/2005 Coll. of 20 May 2005)

4.4. Other sources

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Antonenkov and Others v. Ukraine, Application no. 14183/02, 2005, available at: [https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#{%22itemid%22:\[%22001-71202%22\]}](https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#{%22itemid%22:[%22001-71202%22]})

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Mangouras v. Spain, Application no. 12050/04, 2009, available at: [https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#{%22itemid%22:\[%22001-90383%22\]}](https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#{%22itemid%22:[%22001-90383%22]})

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Greek case: Decision no. 359/2021 (the 9th Athens Investigating Judge)

Slovakian case: No. 3 Tost 34/2020 (Supreme Court)

Slovakian case: 39Tp/13/2020, available at:

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Polish case: II AKz 327/20 (Court of Appeal in Szczecin)